

Spectrophotometric determination of vanadium in industrial effluents around Raipur area

S. K. Rajput, Deepthi Bansode^{a*} and Sunita Nair

^aGovt. Nagarjuna P.G. College of Science, Raipur-492 010, Chhattisgarh, India

E-mail : adeptcreative@gmail.com

Department of Chemistry, SSN College of Engineering, Kalavakkam-603 110, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : sunitanair@ssn.edu.in

Manuscript received 02 November 2010, revised 18 January 2012, accepted 25 January 2012

Abstract : A selective and sensitive spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of total amount of vanadium in the selected industrial site discharges. The proposed method quantitatively determines trace amounts of vanadium, which forms a purple colored complex with *N*-phenyl 3-methylbenzohydroxamic acid, having λ_{\max} at 475 nm. The optimum reaction conditions and other important analytical parameters have been investigated. The present method is successfully applied for the analysis of vanadium in industrial effluents around Raipur area.

Keywords : Spectrophotometric, selective, sensitive, discharges, hydroxamic acid.

Introduction

Vanadium is a soft, ductile, silver-grey metal. It has good resistance to corrosion and it is stable against alkalis, sulfuric and hydrochloric acids. It is oxidized in air at about 933 K (660 °C), although an oxide layer forms even at room temperature. Vanadium is reported to be a toxic as well as an essential trace element for all living beings¹. Bones and teeth may use vanadium as a building material. Vanadium also plays a role in blood sugar balance and cardiovascular function. Vanadium compounds have been proven to be associated with various implications in the pathogenesis of some human diseases and also in maintaining normal body functions². Many methods are available in the literature for the trace determina-

tion of vanadium in the given sample but they are rather very lengthy and involve the removal of interfering ions by solvent extraction^{3,4}. Various spectrophotometric methods have also been reported⁵⁻⁷. These methods are based on the formation of colored complexes with organic reagent hydroxamic acids^{8,9}, such as *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid¹⁰, benzohydroxamic acid¹¹ and *N*-phenylcinnamohydroxamic acid¹². In the present studies, a new heterocyclic hydroxamic acid, namely, *N*-phenyl 3-methylbenzohydroxamic acid (PMBHA) is used as a complexing reagent. This reagent forms a purple colored complex with vanadium in acidic medium which can be utilized as a colorimetric reagent for the spectrophotometric determination.

Chemical reaction

Results and discussion

The PMBHA instantaneously reacted with V^{5+} in the presence of $CHCl_3$ and concentrated HCl to give a purple colored complex having λ_{max} at 475 nm. The absorbance of the purple colored complex remains stable for 30 min. Various acids such as H_2SO_4 , CH_3COOH were also tested for the formation of purple colored complex in aqueous solution, but it was only stable with HCl. The optimum pH range for color development was found to be between 2 and 3 and beyond this, the absorbance of the complex was decreased.

Table 1. Optical densities and concentration (composition) of vanadium from standard calibration curve

Sl. no.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
1.	10	0.09
2.	20	0.32
3.	30	0.27
4.	40	0.36
5.	50	0.44
6.	60	0.59
7.	70	0.62
8.	80	0.69
9.	90	0.76
10.	100	0.8

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of vanadium-PMBHA complex.

The system obeyed Lambert Beer's law in the concentration range of $0.2\text{--}1.6 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are $2.6 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0136 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The ratio of vanadium(V)

to PMBHA in the complex was determined as 1 : 1 by curve fitting method¹³.

The values of concentration and optical densities were recorded (Table 1). A standard calibration curve was plotted between concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) of vanadium and optical density, which is a straight line (Fig. 2). In order to assess the validity of the method, industrial effluents were collected from different sites around Raipur area. The calibration curve in the range of 0 to $10 \mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration was plotted again (the dotted portion in Fig. 1). The optical densities of the collected samples were plotted on y-axis, and the values of the concentration of vanadium (in $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were noted from the x-axis of the graph (Fig. 3). These observations are recorded in Table 2.

Experimental

A standard solution of ammonium metavanadate (AMV) was prepared in distilled water. Aliquots of standard AMV were taken in measuring flasks and diluted with distilled water to make different concentration of vanadium ranging from 10 to $100 \mu\text{g/ml}$. Different concentration of vanadium, each of 2 ml, is pipetted out in a series of stoppered test tubes and labeled them accordingly. To these test tubes 5 ml of $CHCl_3$, 4 ml of concentrated HCl and 1 ml of 1% *N*-phenyl 3-methylbenzohydroxamic acid were added. The absorbance of purple colored complex was measured at 475 nm against reagent blank.

Systronic microprocessor ore based UV-Visible spectrophotometer Model No. 117 was used for all spectral measurements. The working pH range was observed to be between 2 and 3.

In this method, most of the common ions present in industrial effluents do not interfere with the determination of vanadium.

The above selected area is then plotted separately (ranging from 0 to $10 \mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration). Now the optical densities of the selected samples (industrial effluent) was plotted and extrapolated towards the concentration axis which gave the concentration in percentage of vanadium in the given samples.

It is apparent from Fig. 2 that UR_2 had a relatively higher concentration of vanadium whereas UR_1 had minimum.

Fig. 2. The calibration graph for vanadium using PMBHA.

Fig. 3. Graph representing concentration of vanadium in industrial effluents.

Table 2. Concentration (composition) of vanadium in industrial effluent

Sl. no.	Industrial effluent source ^a	Concentration (µg/ml)
1.	UR ₁	2.0
2.	UR ₂	6.3
3.	UR ₃	3.0
4.	UR ₄	3.3
5.	UR ₅	4.0

^aUrta site industrial effluent.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. K. N. Bapat, Principal, Govt. Nagarjuna P.G. College of Science and Raipur

Institute of Technology, Mandirhasaud, Raipur for providing necessary facilities.

References

1. F. A. Patty, "Industrial Hygiene and Toxicology", Vol. III, Interscience Publisher, New York, 1963, 1174.
2. Biswajit Mukherjee, Balaram Patra, Sushmita Mahapatra, Pratik Banerjee, Amit Tiwari and Malay Chatterjee, *Toxicology Letters*, 2004, **150**, 135.
3. M. Siroki and C. Djordjevic, *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 1971, **57**, 301.
4. O. Menis and C. S. P. Iyer, *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 1971, **55**, 89.
5. M. Assefaand and B. S. Chandravanshi, *Miko. Chem. Acta*, 1983, **1**, 255.
6. A. K. Shrivastava, *Int. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.*, 1986, **1**, 27.
7. C. L. Chakrabarti, R. J. Magee and C. L. Wilson, *Talanta*, 1968, **34**, 402.
8. U. Priyadarshini and S. G. Tandon, *Analyst*, 1961, **86**, 544.
9. A. Sao, A. Pillai and V. K. Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 400.
10. D. E. Ryan, *Analyst*, 1960, **85**, 569.
11. Z. Marczenko, "Spectrophotometric Determination of Elements", Wiley, New York, 1976.
12. Y. K. Agrawal, *Acta Lett.*, 1972, **5**, 563.
13. L. C. Sillen, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1956, **10**, 185.

